

HEALTHY EATING-A GUARANTEE OF HEALTH

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ABSTRACT

Currently, the focus on the rules of proper nutrition has risen to the level of public policy. A number of decrees and resolutions of the head of our state are aimed at improving the health care system and promoting a healthy lifestyle among the population, including rational nutrition. For this reason, in this article we will look at the effect of nutrition on the body, the rules of proper nutrition and its basics.

The concept of a healthy lifestyle has a wide meaning, it is associated with physical activity, rational eating, harmful habits, namely addiction, smoking tobacco, alcohol consumption covers activities such as combating. At this point, the one that affects the human body eating in thousands of factors, especially in time and in moderation, and when necessary, dietebop it should be borne in mind that the consumption of dishes is of paramount importance. Nutrition medical point of view considering age, body weight, gender, climatic conditions, location of the disease in the body, its taking into account the type and period, a recommendation in different procedures and composition for the Prevention of the disease are. Only then can a person live a long, healthy and prosperous life.

By most rational nutrition, eating tasty, nutritious, high-calorie foods implies making. Individuals are disorganized (nahorda or in the evening before bedtime) eat food.

In fact, the food consumed ensures that the body is restored to the energy lost if it satisfies the excess, it contains the necessary amount of proteins, fats, carbohydrates, vitamins, micro and if macronutrients, plant fibers are stored, and food and their composition, amount coincide with the activity of enzymes of the digestive system-the so - called rational nutrition.

From the energy that each person spends and receives throughout the night it is possible to draw up a diet of food. Proteins contained in foods consumed, fats, carbohydrates, vitamins, minerals and water should be in proportion to each other. Eating food at a certain time of the day-this makes it possible to form conditioned reflexes it also prepares the body for food intake. Breakfast and lunch, lunch and dinner the interval time is 3-4 hours, dinner should be consumed at least 3 hours before sleep must. 4 meals a day - about 25 percent of it to the first breakfast, 15 percent for the second breakfast, 35 percent for lunch, 25 percent for dinner. 5 in some cases it is recommended to eat once-about 25 percent in it to the first

breakfast, 15 percent to the second to breakfast, 35 percent to lunch, 20 percent to dinner, 5 percent to dinner before bedtime needed.

It is very important to pay attention to its component when eating. Because protein-rich nutrients increase the excitability of the nervous system, make them in the first half of the day, or human it is better to eat during the period of active movement. Otherwise it will lead to sleep disturbances.

When dinner makes up most of the daily diet, the breakdown of fats is complete unobserved, it causes a tendency to obesity. Sufficient in the body, i.e. expendable and when the power obtained from food is balanced, a person is healthy and long-lived.

The calories you take in excess of what you need can lead to obesity, increased blood pressure and other the row leads to cardiovascular diseases. Less than normal intake of calories, however the basis for a decrease in the body's protective-adaptive capabilities and the occurrence of diseases creates. In such cases, the process of growth and development in the children's body is lagging behind.

In general, the proportion of proteins falling with food is in the range of 10-15 percent, the proportion of fats No more than 30 percent, while the percentage of carbohydrates should be up to 55-65 percent. Daily food volume

Eating no less than 60 percent in the first half of the day-breakfast and lunch recommended. Breaks between meals should not exceed 3-4 hours. Time to eat it is necessary that all food is enough to be eaten unhurried and thoroughly chewed. Rush when eating, a person eats more food than he needs, because this is the time for satiety relatively late and, according to the law of inverse negative contact, glucose and amino acids in the blood with concentration, the behavioral signal is transmitted late to the brain. Also, the food is good it does not crumble and is not soaked with saliva, as a result of which it is digested in the stomach and intestines it worsens to be and be absorbed.

Dietary nutrition is the satisfaction of the physiological need of the body in relation to nutrients and the therapeutic effect on the course of the disease is considered. The diet is primarily infected in nutrition chemical, thermal and mechanical advance of the organ, exchange of one product for another or patient it is assumed that the necessary nutrients will be introduced into the body.

In place of the conclusion, it is worth saying that in order for the body to grow normally, to function normally, it is necessary to consume food in a more rational standard.

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